

IMPLEMENT THE CONCEPT OF NATIONAL GROWTH THE NEED TO TRANSFORM INCREASE INTO A NATIONAL MOVEMENT

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Annotation: In this article, the importance of implementing the concept of national rise, the rise in society serves the stage of national rise from national revival by effectively applying the creative activities of individuals to the fields. In turn, the development of programs that serve to ensure the development of the society and the prevention of social problems are discussed.

Key words and phrases: concept of national growth, new development, modern outlook, scientific-theoretical views, continuous education, individual qualities, well-rounded person, educational standards, civil society, scientific-methodology.

Introduction At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the great works being carried out to restore our national spirituality, which has a rich history that has been hidden from our people, to develop it in the direction of the country's development, thinking about the future of our people, as well as the tasks ahead of us in this regard, have been determined. In the current conditions, when fundamental changes are being implemented in all aspects of society's life, and market relations are gaining priority, it is important that strong social policy is one of the main principles of our development. Social policy is understood as caring for the people - every social group, stratum, class, every citizen, young and old, male and female, carrying out reforms and economic activities in the interests of the people, not reducing attention to the fields of public education, health care, culture, and science.

The conclusion that the initiator of reforms should be the people and the society and for the sake of the people, to increase their well-being and live a decent life, constitutes the meaning of social policy. This means the humanitarian nature of our state's policy. In the process of building a new society, the following activities aimed at continuing a strong socially oriented policy are being held.

Ensuring the gradual and consistent improvement of the material well-being of the people, creating the necessary conditions for our compatriots to live a decent life and grow up, creates the need to further improve the well-directed mechanism of social protection of the population, first of all, its layers that need help - young children, the elderly, the disabled, and students. The family, which is the sacred fortress and the cradle of spirituality for our people, is to strengthen the fact that the family and its foundation are the foundation of the society, while continuing the work carried out in the field of increasing the place and position of our mothers and women in the society. The more stable, prosperous and advanced the family is, the more stable and progressive the society will be. Large-scale projects and radical changes implemented in society will be successful if they also strengthen, improve, or do not negatively affect the foundations of the family. Improving the functioning of state structures that guarantee the legal equality of citizens and the rule of law, the interests of society and the

safety of the population more effectively is an important sign of the social sphere. At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, considering that the state will be able to build a healthy ideologically and spiritually mature generation, strengthening the work on educating a perfect person in perspective and at the level of state policy and turning it into a national movement is closely related to national growth. That is why raising a mature generation, who is mentally mature, mentally fresh and healthy, free and critical thinker, and at the same time has a proper sense of social responsibility, who has acquired a certain profession, is becoming a component, the main condition and goal of building a new society in Uzbekistan. In order to accomplish such a complex task, the field of education is being fundamentally reformed. These reforms are implemented on the basis of the new law "On Education". A new approach to such education will be an innovative way to transform the implementation of the concept of national development into a nationwide movement.

In the process of establishing a new society, first of all, it is necessary to be able to correctly evaluate spiritual values. When assessing a certain value, the main criterion should be the extent to which it can strengthen the political, economic, social and moral foundations of the independent development of our country, and serve to make our nation an active subject of global social development.

Methods Humanism, patriotism, nationalism and progressiveness are the criteria of the main principles of a correct approach to national values, including cultural heritage on a scientific basis. In each of these criteria, nationalism and universality are embodied, creating a basis for national growth. Although they have essentially a universal character, they reveal the needs of specific peoples in each historical period and serve to satisfy them. Therefore, the essence of universal humanity, embodied in their core, emerges by expressing national needs in a specific national form and adapting its content to them. These criteria are not only national and universal, but also historic. That is, they are enriched and improved in proportion to the requirements of the times and the new tasks facing the society, not in accordance with the patterns that have become rigid in form and content.

As in all spheres, the work in the religious and educational sphere remains in the pages of history with the rise of efficiency to a new level. For example, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Acting President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who took part in the opening ceremony of the Council of Foreign Ministers of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, which started its work in Tashkent, stated in his speech that the theme "Education and enlightenment - the road to peace and creativity" is the main idea of the agenda of the 43rd session, which has a deep symbolic meaning. This idea is consistent with the famous hadith "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave".[1] The tasks defined in the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on June 15, 2017 at the conference on the topic "Ensuring social stability, preserving the purity of our holy religion - the need of the times" include "Hadith studies at the Imam Bukhari Scientific Center in Samarkand, Kalam science at the Imam Motrudi Center, School of Islamic Law at the Ferganada-Marginani Scientific Center, Bukhara-Ba If we establish Sufism in Naqshband center and Aqeedah school in Kashkadarya-Abu Muin Nasafi center, I think it will be very useful" and the fifth priority of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", ensuring security, inter-ethnic harmony and deeply defined religious tolerance, It is expressed by the need to strengthen the independence and sovereignty of our country, to create an environment of security, stability and

harmonious neighborhood around Uzbekistan, to strengthen the international prestige of our country, aimed at conducting a thoughtful, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy.

The government, which is mobilizing all its strength and opportunity so that the Uzbek people are not inferior to anyone else in the world, and the young generation lives educated, wise and happy, pays special attention to the issue of spiritual education in this regard. At this point, the need to turn the implementation of the concept of national development into a nationwide movement is undoubtedly of incomparable importance. If we lose our vigilance and sensitivity, our determination and responsibility in this matter, if we leave this extremely important work to its own devices, if we lose our spirituality, which is fed by our sacred values and are nourished by them, we will lose our historical memory, and in the end, it is inevitable that we will deviate from the path of universal development that we strive for.

Cultural changes taking place in the world call every patriotic citizen of our country to be vigilant. Because there is no integrated system for the organization of spiritual and educational processes, insufficient organizational-practical and scientific-research works are not being carried out to protect our people, especially young people, from spiritual threats, the fact that the social cooperation of state organizations, civil society institutions, mass media and the private sector has not been effectively established in this direction[2], it is necessary to determine the need for national development today. Uzbekistan is on the way to transition to market relations, to build a legal democratic state, to educate young people who think in a new way, with a new attitude to work, to restore our national and spiritual values, and to create comfortable living conditions for our people. Of course, many people understand very well that this work is extremely complicated, there are a number of difficulties, especially in the mind of our people, it is necessary to change according to the times.

These changes are related to raising the moral life of society and spiritual education. A great role in introducing Uzbekistan to the world, in introducing the people of the world to the great work being carried out in our country, in explaining to the peoples of the world that the high spirituality characteristic of our people is not in vain, that it has historical, philosophical and religious roots that have been formed over the centuries.

Results The importance of the idea "from national revival to national rise" is considered a great historical event in the history of our country, and this historical process will be a solid foundation for the long-term development of our nation. Strengthening independence is one of the dreams of our people, and today it is the duty and responsibility of all citizens to protect it and ensure its eternal existence. The achievement of Uzbek independence created great opportunities and conditions for the republic to choose its own socio-economic and political-legal development path, to have its own decisive path. National growth is the main basis of the path chosen by Uzbekistan, commitment to humanitarian ideals, determination of the rules of freedom of conscience and religion, and realization of the principles of social justice. At the moment, laying the foundation stone for the national idea and national ideology, studying the history of the Motherland and taking it to the path of independent development are of great importance at the level of state policy.

For the above reasons, the following are targeted for implementation at the state level. "Regardless of nationality, language and religion, every person living in our country should live a free, peaceful and prosperous life, living contentedly with today's life is becoming the main goal of the state. The Sustainable Development Goals until 2030 are implemented in our country based on the principle of "leaving no one behind", which provides for the protection

of the rights and legal interests of every person. Organizational and legal measures are being implemented to strengthen the role of parliament, civil society institutions, and mass media, and to implement the principles of "The people are literally the only source and author of laws" and "All important decisions are made on the basis of direct dialogue with the people, taking into account the opinion of the public" [3]. Bigotry in socio-political life, in turn, has a great impact on the development of all forms of social consciousness. In order to turn the implementation of the concept of national development into a nationwide movement, first of all, the legal state, that is, the rule of law, is an important theoretical and practical basis for society. Ensuring the observance of human rights and freedoms, respecting the dignity of each person is an integral feature of the open, free and fair society we are building.[4] That is, it is understood that openness and justice are important features. At this place, Socrates states that "Lawfulness is an indicator of justice, justice and any virtue consists of knowledge, and anything done through virtue is spiritual beauty." Plato understood the rule of law and a just society in his own way, "Where the laws do not have force or are under someone's judgment, I believe that the state is close to destruction. Where the law rules over the rulers, and the rulers are the slaves of the laws, that is where the state flourishes." This will be a protective tool for regular study of geopolitical and ideological processes, effective ideological struggle against terrorism, extremism, fanaticism, human trafficking, drug business and other dangerous threats, and development of international cooperation in this regard.

The role of the national development model is important in the development of society. Because the national development model means the ways of social-political, legal, economic and spiritual development approved by the people, the nation, the methods of state management, regional and global integration strategy. It is a conceptual idea arising from the internal nature of the national state's internal and external policy, a theoretical model of development, and a collection of mechanisms for solving practical problems. At the center of it are the interests of national development, measures to express and protect these interests.

If legal culture is one of the foundations of national growth, then legal culture is the embodiment of legal thinking, legal technique (advancement) and legal experience, and in others, it is evaluated as one of the forms of socially significant creative activity in the field of legal relations of the population, and if it is expressed as the ability to evaluate these phenomena in the institutions of legal norms, then its components justify national growth.

The revival of the nation during a certain stage of its historical development, which takes place in the life of this nation, is deprived of its heritage, customs, traditions, and values, its historical memory is crushed, its national identity is limited, its interests, goals are lost, and its national development is the result of gaining its independence. It is a process of nationwide activity aimed at using these opportunities and directing all the created material and spiritual wealth to national development.

The main direction of national revitalization is related to the process of national and national identity awareness, which is to turn the opportunities lost by one or another nation in terms of national development at a certain stage of historical development into the main source of national development again with the honor of gaining independence.

Discussion The need to turn the implementation of the concept of national development into a nationwide movement is realized by the construction of civil society. Therefore, civil society is a legitimate stage, the highest form of self-expression of individuals. Institutions of civil society, in particular, non-governmental organizations, initially appeared

on the basis of the needs and interests of self-management of society and ensuring its existence as an independent social unit, ... eliminating barriers between the state and individual citizens, democracy from below

ensures its development. Also, at the modern stage of the country's development, it requires the successful implementation of large-scale reforms and the creation of a completely new, effective and high-quality functioning system of state administration, the organization of harmonious activities of state administration bodies and local executive authorities. Efforts are being made to successfully implement the state policy on modernization of economic sectors and social sphere, comprehensive development of regions, improvement of the standard of living and well-being of the population. Violation of compatibility between needs and acquisition, that is, the inability of acquisition to satisfy needs or the emergence of new needs, leads to the change and development of cultural existence. The expansion of the scope of cultural existence can be the basis for the development of society, social, including legal development. As a result, democracy develops, political culture and activity of the population increases. A legal guarantee will appear for the development of the diversity of opinions and the diversity of views, and for the establishment of ideological pluralism. Human rights are ensured in society. Illegal benefits or, on the contrary, discrimination will be put an end to. What is important is that the interests of individuals, all social groups and strata are fully taken into account, and their creative potential is effectively realized. The role and importance of public organizations is increasing year by year. A society that meets the requirements of civil society will be built. Therefore, the principle of the rule of law, in a broad sense, serves social development, renewal of society, and the rise of human personality in Uzbekistan. It complements the state's activities in the management of public affairs, because civil society institutions, due to their scale, mass and flexibility, need to identify the problems that arise in social life and act effectively in places where the capabilities of state agencies are limited, especially at the local level.[5]

The need to turn the concept of national rise into a nationwide movement is related to deepening the process of democratization of society's life, ensuring its consistency and effectiveness - the main direction of the political reforms implemented in the country. The strategy of new Uzbekistan is to expand the participation of citizens in the social and political life of the country, to realize their dreams, to implement advanced initiatives, to solve their life problems, to raise their standard of living, and to create sufficient and necessary conditions for them to independently increase their material well-being. At the new stage of development, liberalization of all spheres of the country's political life, state and society building, increasing political activity of the population, formation of a political culture based on national and universal values, and the essence of the features of the national idea in the political sphere are manifested in these.

The development of statehood and its development criteria are determined by the moral level of the nation. After all, the history of the development of peoples who are aware of their identity, are united in common goals, have harmonious goals, are superior in honor, and have a culture of a single profession, has been proven in the experiences of human societies. Today, the strategic policy of the country is expanding the possibilities of understanding the political-social, spiritual-cultural heritage of our national statehood on the basis of a new way of thinking and applying it directly to the management of the society, and entering into the integration of the world community.

National growth and development is a type of changes and actions that take place in nature and society during the transition from one quality to another or from one state to another. According to the dominant concepts of philosophy, the development of matter and consciousness as a whole is spirally infinite. For, while its regression and stagnation are recognized, its principles grow from simplicity to complex forms. That is, its development is based on the activities of the object itself. We express it by "innovations", "concepts" related to the development of society.

In addition, any development process begins with social change. Changes are made through social, economic, spiritual, cultural and political spheres. That is, as a result of the exchange of the quantitative, meaningful and structural state of each field, quality indicators are created. However, any changes do not ensure development. Changes lead to development in social and public integrity. Thus, in the process of complexification and improvement of the social system, development is manifested in its effective adaptability to external conditions, in the expansion of the scope of reality, in the growth of the number in any field, and in the creation of structural structures for its practical support.

According to the experience of developed and highly developed countries, each nation enters the world community with great and promising goals and the potential to realize them. Therefore, going through the processes of natural development is characteristic of all peoples, but the selection, implementation and provision of the paths of transition are determined by the national and cultural characteristics of the society. That is, these goals are expressed in the strategic directions of the state.

Conclusion In conclusion, the need to turn the implementation of the concept of national growth into a nationwide movement is determined by the fact that the fundamental reforms implemented in the country are fully consistent with the strategic doctrines. And this important strategic goals will start a completely new stage of development of the society. The idea of national growth, which is the basis for the rise of the state and society, has an incomparable place in raising the development of our country to a new level, in taking bold steps towards innovative development. The driving force of the national development strategy is the goal of the state and its bodies. Strategic national growth is considered a pledge and guarantee of reforms as a phenomenon of social growth.

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